

- Subject: List and comparison of software for forward and inverse modelling in geophysics.

The subject is related to the diversity of software available for forward and inverse modelling in geophysics with a specific focus for archaeological applications. It is intended to make a list of them in a first step (some work is already available by the author of this call and some wiki pages) and a comparison between them with a focus on their use for detectability of archaeological structures (prediction of magnitude and shape of anomalies) and their usability (environment, ergonomics, etc.). The most used methods (magnetics, resistivity, low frequency EM and GPR) are the main methods looked for. This study does not limit itself to open-source software, but also includes freeware software. Visualization software is not part of the scope of this call.

- Outcome: List and comparison of software for archaeological surveys. Simulation on a synthetic case with computation of limiting factors for detectability.

People who have answered by email about their use of software for modelling/inversion of geophysical data are listed here by chronological order:

- **Mercedes Solla Carracelas** (2/10/2019) about radar: GPRSIM, REFLEXW, GPRMAX.
- **Roman Pasteka** (4/10/2019) about gravimetry and magnetics : Potent software by Geophysical Software solutions(Australia), GM-SYS by Northwest Geophysical Associates Inc (USA), GMM modelling by G-Trend Ltd Slovakia, Mod3D open-source, IGMAS+/-
- **Apostolos Sarris** (4/10/2019) about radar: GPRMAX and ReflexW.
- **Julien Thiesson** (7/10/2019) about electric and EM: PyGimli/PyBert (Thomas Gunthe et al.) + home-made software by A. Tabbagh in Fortran for resistivity and EM modelling; open source code FDEM1D by Ghent University.
- **Ilaria Catapano** (8/10/2019) about radar: VIY3 by Transient (but linked only to this instrument), GRED/3D by IDS, open source microwave tomographic approach for GPR by Ilaria on-line soon.
- **Nikos Papadopoulos** (8/10/2019) about electric : Res2DInv and Res3DInv by geotomosoft, EarthImager2D and 3D by Advances Geosciences, DC_2DPRO and DC_3DPRO by Korean Institute of Geosciences, 2DIP and TS2DIP by Zonge, SensInv2D and 3D by Crosswellinstruments- Germany, BERT Boundless Electrical Resistivity Tomography, R3t and R2 freeware by Univ. of Lancaster.
- **Merik Berge** (9/10/2019): Res1D, Res2Dmod, Res3Dmod, R2, R3t, pyGimli-Bert for resistivity; ReflexW, GPRSIM and GPRMax for radar, MAG2DATA and Potensoft for magnetics, ReflexW for seismics, Inv2DVLF for EM, Potensoft for gravity.
- **Armin Schmidt** (22/12/2019): magnetometer modelling and inversion with home-made software programmed in Python using the very advanced SciPy library.

The resistivity section has been corrected by Nikos Papadopoulos.

It seems that a comparison between different software for geophysical modelling specifically for archaeological applications does not exist as such.

On Wikipedia, there exists a list of open-source software (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_free_and_open-source_software_packages) or specialized lists like for GIS : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Free_GIS_software, or for topics in geophysics: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparison_of_free_geophysics_software.

But looking at the software listed, the great majority of them is related to seismic data and is of little use for archaeological / soil researches.

Looking at places like Sourceforge, and using the word 'geophysics' (<https://sourceforge.net/directory/os:windows/?q=geophysics>) returns only 8 projects, most of them having not been alive for more than 4 years (except GPLib++, but used for MT and seismic). The GitHub repository (<https://github.com/search?q=geophysics>) hosts more code related to geophysics (508 in March 2020) and it is necessary to refine the query to a specific method (electromagnetics for example) to see all projects on this platform.

The work undertaken in this report is a list of software for forward and inverse modelling in geophysics for archaeology.

First, we have asked our colleagues which software they have used or were still using for modelling the response of archaeological structures and for the inversion of geophysical anomalies. We have mainly focused on free software, but some commercial one were also included if their price was relatively low. In a second step, we have been looking through Internet sources to gather information about different modelling software.

Considering the number of software packages found (nearly 30), it was not possible to download every software and test it (a call for students with STSMs was unsuccessful). The following tables and notes were derived only from literature and from my personal experience. But we hope that they could be used as a first base of thought for the use of these software packages. The final table (XLS file) mimics what has already been done for wikis about free and open-source software.

ELECTROMAGNETICS

Despite instruments used for a long time (Geonics EM31 for example), this method is probably the one which has the least software available. Among the different responses obtained from our questionnaire, only two software packages were quoted (Inv2DVLF and pyGIMLi).

- Inv2DVLF is an inversion code for single frequency VLF data (we will not discuss in detail VLF data, because the method is very rarely used in geophysics applied to archaeology). It was developed by Monteiro Santos et al. in 2016 following the resolution of the direct problem using finite element modelling by Sasaki (ref: <http://emtomo.com/news-and-events/42-a-new-version-of-the-vlf2d-em-multifrequency>).
- A new version for multifrequency data is now available: VLF2Dmf (<http://emtomo.com/products/vlf2dmf>). It includes a 2D forward modelling and 2D Occam inversion of VLF-EM data including topography. This software is not free, but we mention it because of the paucity of available LFEM software.

- EM4 soil from the same company (EMTOMO) is a program for 1D Laterally Constrained Inversion (or quasi-2D inversion) and 1D Spatially Constrained Inversion (quasi-3D inversion) of data collected with multisensor and multifrequency instruments like those from DUALEM, GEONICS, GF-CMD or GEM and GSSI-Profiler. This software is not free (<http://emtomo.com/products/em4soil>).
- AarhusInv (<https://hgg.au.dk/software/aarhus-workbench>) is a package used for inversion of several types of data (ERT, IP and EMI). AarhusInv uses a local 1D model description. In the inversion phase, the models are constrained together forming a 3D-model space. For DC and IP a full 2D solution is available as well. Although AarhusInv is free to use for non-commercial purposes, one needs to sign and return a registration form to receive AarhusInv (Auken et al., 2016). The AarhusInv program is a stand-alone command-prompt executable, written in Fortran. It runs on Windows platforms.
- EMMA ElectroMagnetic Model Analysis from Aarhus University (<https://hgg.au.dk/software/emma>) is a freeware for analysis of electrical and electromagnetic modelling (both TDEM and FDEM). It can be used as a planning and teaching application. Registered users receive the EMMA newsletter and information about new versions. The underlying model is a 1-D model with horizontal layers. It is an executable file for Windows.
- PyGIMLi (<https://www.pygimli.org>): GIMLi is a general library for modelling and inversion in geophysics (Rucker et al., 2017). This object-oriented library provides management for structured and unstructured meshes in 2D and 3D, finite-element and finite-volume solvers, various geophysical forward operators, as well as Gauss-Newton based frameworks for constrained, joint and fully-coupled inversions with flexible regularization. It is available for different platforms (Linux, Windows, Mac) and requires Python3. PyGIMLi is distributed under the terms of the Apache 2.0 license. Its use is reserved for people with skills in computing and physics. GIMLi is very well documented (manual of more than 500 pages, examples, on-line resources, etc.).
- We also want to mention the code from Hanssens (Ghent University). He has made it available on GitHub (<https://github.com/dhanssens/FDEM1D>) in November 2018. It is a 1D forward and sensitivity modelling code for a 1D multi-layered-space. Conductivity, susceptibility and permittivity of the different layers can be changed. Code is written both in Python 3 and MatlabR2016 and necessitates one of these software packages.

General comments:

Most of the researchers we know use their own routines. It must be pointed that the full resolution of Maxwell equations is difficult and some simplifications has been used for a long time following the work of Geonics in Canada. Using these simple equations (for example the cumulative response for Horizontal coplanar or vertical coplanar configurations) is straightforward but is an approximation (Born). To our knowledge

only the team of A. Tabbagh/ J. Thiesson in Paris-Sorbonne University and J. Guillemoteau / Tronicke in Potsdam University have resolved the full problem for archaeological applications (Guillemoteau *et al.*, 2016). The Paris team has made pieces of software available (written in Fortran77) on request. There is no graphical interface and input and output of data is not straightforward. We have no information about Guillemoteau's software. Most of the software quoted is only modelling 1D cases with lateral constraints making them quasi-2D case. The Aarhus software seems to us one of the best available software packages even if we have not tested it.

N.B. To keep updated about new open-source software browse for example: <https://github.com/search?q=geophysics+electromagnetics> .

SEISMICS

There are a lot of seismic packages available (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparison_of_free_geophysics_software) but to our questionnaire only one name was cited: ReflexW.

- ReflexW is a program for processing and interpretation of GPR data, seismic and ultrasound data with different geometry configurations (reflection, refraction, borehole cross-hole and tomography - 2D and 3D cases). The program is very stable and has been refined since more than 20 years by Sandmeier (REFLEXW is written with Delphi 5/DelphiXE2). (<https://www.sandmeier-geo.de/reflexw.html>). The software is licenced and includes a discount for academic licences and also free updates for 5 years after purchase. It runs only under Windows. There exist many pdf guides and videos.
- PyGIMLi (see ELECTROMAGNETICS section).

General comments:

We did not spend much time to browse most of the available software in seismics because of the rare use of this method for archaeological investigations. ReflexW is a long-time stable software perfectly suited for 2D and 3D analysis that can also be used for GPR processing.

MAGNETICS AND GRAVIMETRY

- MG2DATA: This open-source code was developed by Stocco *et al.*, 2009 in Matlab. It allows the forward model and the inversion of 2D and 2.5D magnetic data of both Total, vertical gradient and vertical component of the magnetic field. Remanent magnetization can be included. This code can only be used for selected magnetic profiles extracted from maps for example to estimate the size and depth of elongated source bodies. This code applies to 2 D and 2.5D structures (2.5D means that the extension of the bodies perpendicular to the profile is not 'infinite' – practically more than 10 times the dimension on-line – but finite).
- Potensoft developed by Arisoy and Dikmen, 2011 is a Matlab code (Version 7.6 Release 2008b) not only for modelling but also processing and mapping gravity and magnetic

data. It runs under Windows but has been tested with Linux. It is easy to use (a well-designed GUI) and is open-source. (Unfortunately the link: <http://www.eng.ankara.edu.tr/~ariso/potensoft.htm> is no longer valid).

- POTENT is a software developed by Geophysical Software Solutions Pty. Ltd. and runs under Windows (<http://www.geoss.com.au/potent.html>). It provides a highly interactive framework for 3-D modelling of magnetic and gravity data. PotentQ, is a simplified and streamlined version of Potent that allows rapid semi-automatic modelling of a single magnetic and/or gravity anomaly (PotentQ has been integrated with Geosoft's Oasis montaj interface, <https://www.geosoft.com/products>). Considering the price for Oasis, we will not discuss this very powerful software. The price of POTENT is also high for a perpetual licence but 30 days or 6 months licences are available.
- GM-SYS from Geosoft (<https://www.geosoft.com/products/gm-sys>) requires the Oasis montaj platform. GM-SYS Profile Modelling provides a wide range of gravity and magnetic mapping, modelling and interpretation capabilities. We have no info about the price, but Oasis Montaj is a pre-requisite. Considering the price of Oasis, we will not discuss this very powerful software.
- GMM, is a software quoted by R. Pasteka, from G-Trend s.r.o. company (www.gtrend.sk) in Slovakia but we haven't found any information on the Internet.
- MOD3D (<https://sourceforge.net/projects/mod3d/>) is a C++ code (by Igor Cerovsky) available on souceforge and GitHub (<https://github.com/igorcerovsky/Mod3D>). It has not been active for 6 years (software developed during his PhD at Bratislava Univ. and Tübingen). The gravity and/or magnetic anomalies are computed using formulae for polyhedral bodies (3D) with a user-friendly interactive environment.
- IGMAS+ software (<http://www.gravity.uni-kiel.de/igmas>) has been developed for more than 20 years by the University of Kiel (Schmidt et al., 2007) and is a new version of IGMAS ("Interactive Geophysical Modelling Application System") with a modern graphical interface and automated interpretation tools. It allows easy integration of constraining data into interactive modelling processes, visualization and combination of geodata with density/susceptibility models. The numerical algorithms were developed by Götze (Götze and Lahmeyer, 1988) and allow the calculation of geoidal undulations, gravity components and all its gradients (FTG), as well as remanent and induced magnetic field components and all its gradients in one program step. The link is not active yet (03/2020).
- GMG (https://btozer.github.io/gmg/html/gmg_documentation.html) is an open-source software with a GUI designed by Uieda (Uieda *et al.*, 2014) for modelling 2D potential field (gravity and magnetic) profiles. It is inspired by GMT and 'Fatiendo a Terra' software. This software also includes functions for loading XY data, seismic reflection SEG-Y data and exploration well horizons. The software therefore provides an integrated geological/geophysical interpretation package. It is multiplatform (Python) and needs an Anaconda Python distribution. On-line documentation is very clear (version 1.0, 2019).

General comment:

There exists a lot of free codes for the modelling of gravity/magnetic anomalies, most of it necessitates a compiler or a Matlab/ Python environment. The high-end products, too expensive for archaeological geophysicists, are used mainly for geological investigations. IGMAS+ software seems to be a good compromise for 3D modelling but its status is not known at present and I was not able to find any trace of the former IGMAS software on the Internet. GMG seems a good software for 2D.

GPR

- ReflexW: see paragraph 'SEISMICS'

- GPRSIM (<https://gpr-survey.com/gprsim.html>) is a completely interactive 2D forward modelling software designed specifically for ground penetrating radar (D. Goodman, 1994). The first version dates back to 1989 and development is continuous at user requests. It is a 2D ray-tracing software that predicts the waveform of microwaves that are reflected, transmitted, refracted and attenuated across model ground structures. The manual is very well documented (with the underlying equations) and those who do not know the 'baby-T-rex' response should have a look at the software manual (free)! The pricing of the software is an annual licence with free updates during one year only.

- GPRSim.NET (<https://www.geoscanners.com/freeware.html>) is a freeware for Windows (executable). It is a single wavelet simulation software (A-scan only, no B-scan like with GPRSIM). It is partially based in the transmission line model and allows up to ten layers to be simulated with frequencies ranging from 200MHz to 2000MHz. It can be used to try out different real world survey scenarios and understand how different center frequency antennas could perform, as well as getting an idea of how the A-scan might look like in given conditions.

- gprMax (<http://www.gprmax.com>) is an open source, Finite-Difference Time-Domain Electromagnetic simulation software (Waren, 2016). It is written in Python with performance-critical parts in Cython (original software was in C). It currently does not have a GUI. This allows it to be very flexible and scriptable. gprMax can be run on either CPU or GPU. gprMax can compute GPR soil response with realistic dielectric and geometrical properties (Giannakis, 2015). Installation and documentations are clearly explained with manuals and videos. To install gprMax from GitHub (<https://github.com/gprmax/gprMax>), you need a Python environment (Anaconda for example) and a C compiler (gcc). The code runs on Windows, Mac or Linux. All commands are command-line-driven and pieces of Python code can also be entered in the input files. Complex EM properties and volume geometries (fractals) can be simulated. The output file uses the widely-supported HDF5 format.

- GPRSlice (<https://gpr-survey.com/index.html>) is not a modelling software (like GPRSIM for example), but it is a comprehensive Windows-based GPR imaging software designed for the creation of 2D/3D subsurface images. It is cited here because it has many options for signal processing available and even 4D options have been recently added. It is in constant development since 1994. Input of data is compatible

with most of the manufacturers of GPR. This software that runs only under Windows has an annual licence and there are extra licence for multi-antenna systems.

- VIY3: We were informed about this package, but it is a Windows-based application solely devoted to set up all features for the VIY3 equipment. This GPR is by an Ukrainian company: Transient Technologies LLC (<https://viy.ua>). The software controls the measurement, uploads data to the computer, saves data, processes and prints all measured data. This package is free but can be used only with GPR data from this manufacturer. It is not a modelling software.

- GRED HD 3D: It is also not a modelling software. The GRED HD software is able to process data collected from all IDS GPR systems (<https://idsgeoradar.com/>). Data are acquired by OneVision software and processed by GRED HD. Objects of any generic shape are able to be directly exported to CAD or GIS maps.

- MATGPR (Release 2 in 2010): is a freeware developed by Andreas Tzani (Univ. of Athens) with MATLAB for the analysis & interpretation of common and single offset GPR data. Modelling is a part of MATGPR which includes two modelling methods: the fast, adjoint split-step approach and the Finite-Difference method. Since version 3, matGPR is no longer distributed under the GNU GPL licence: it is now a copyrighted software (see <http://users.uoa.gr/~atzanis/matgpr/matgpr.html> for more details). A standalone version (without MATLAB) is available. The project seems to have stopped since 2016.

- RGPR (<https://github.com/emanuelhuber/RGPR>) is a free and open-source software package to read, export, analyse, process and visualise 2D GPR data (Huber and Hans, 2018). Being written in R, it is multi-platform and necessitates R or R-Studio. There is a well-documented on-line documentation (<http://emanuelhuber.github.io/RGPR>). There are no modelling possibilities. A 3D version has been announced (03/2020).

General comments:

There exists much free code for the modelling of GPR anomalies. A Python/Matlab environment is generally needed. gprMax seems to be the only software able to deal with complex EM properties and volume geometries like those that we encounter in archaeological prospecting. But its use is complex and there is no graphical interface at this time. MatGPR is certainly simpler to use – but restricted to 2D cases- with a standalone version (without Matlab). We have no information if this project is still alive.

ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY and INDUCED POLARISATION

- invVERIS: The inversion procedure used in this software is a 1-dimensional spatially constrained technique (1-D SCI). This method is also known as Quasi-3D (Q3D) inversion. The forward modelling of invVERIS is based upon solutions of DC fields in a layered earth. The inversion algorithm is based upon the Occam regularization method. This software is commercially available (<http://emtomo.com/products/43-invveris>) and is linked to data acquired only with the different VERIS systems (<https://www.veristech.com/the-sensors>).

- EMMA (see in ELECTROMAGNETICS paragraph).
- BERT (<https://gitlab.com/resistivity-net/bert>): BERT builds upon the framework of PyGIMLi (see ELECTROMAGNETICS paragraph) and provides numerous high-level and user-friendly functions and applications specifically tailored for DC resistivity studies. It has originally been programmed as C++ app based on the pyGIMLi core library but is increasingly using Python through pyGIMLi and pybert. Future versions (V3) will be only in Python. To install BERT, GIMLi is needed first. The most comfortable way (available under Linux and Windows) to install BERT is via an Anaconda distribution.
- RES1D by Dr. M.H.Loke - Geotomo Software - (<https://www.geotomosoft.com/downloads.php>) is a free non-commercial Windows program released for academic use. It is a 1D resistivity, IP and SIP direct and inverse modelling software. Note that only Wenner and Schlumberger arrays are available.
- RES2DMOD/3DMOD also by M.H. Loke (<https://www.geotomosoft.com/downloads.php>) is a free non-commercial Windows program released for academic use (32 bits). It is a 2D/3D resistivity and IP direct modelling software (no inversion). More electrode configurations are available than in Res1D and even arbitrary positions are possible. A commercial 64 bits version for Res3DMOD capable of modelling non-standard electrode geometries is also available.
- RES2DINV/3DINV also by M.H. Loke (<https://www.geotomosoft.com/downloads.php>) is designed to invert and interpret tomographic electrical and IP data in 2D, 3D and 4D. The inversion of the resistivity and IP data is conducted by least-square methods involving finite-element and finite-difference methods (a priori information can be used). Any type of electrode position is possible (including borehole and under water electrodes) and time-lapse inversion is possible. It is a commercial Windows software package protected by a serial number. The software has been taken on by Aarhus Geosoftware thus an annual fee has to be considered for latest updates. The licence enable free updates for one year. A free demo version is available (with limitations, but it can be very helpful).
- DC-2DPro / 3DPro: this software for 2D and 3D inversion is developed by Prof. Jung-Ho Kim from KIGAM, the Korean Institute of Geoscience and Mineral Resources (Kim, 2009). It is based on a Finite-Element Method to solve the forward resistivity problem and an active constraint balancing approach incorporating L1 and L2 regularization for fine inverse solutions. It used to be commercially available. The status right now is not known since Dr. Jung-Ho Kim has recently passed away (Papadopoulos, pers. com.).
- SensInv2D/3D is a Windows inversion and modelling software (based on subroutines provided by Peter Dietrich) for 2D/3D resistivity data). This software can be purchased theoretically from Geotomographie (<http://geotomographie.de>), but I found a possibility through the Harbourdom company (<http://www.harbourdom.de/sensiv2d.htm>). This is

actually an old software that uses approximate inversion methods (Back Projection, SIRT and MSIRT).

- 2DIP/TS2DIP is a Windows commercial software from Zonge (<http://zonge.com/instruments-home/software/modelling-ip>) for 2D forward and inverse modelling (resistivity + IP).
- EarthImager2D/3D is a Windows commercial software from Advanced Geosciences Inc. (<https://www.agiusa.com/products/software>) for 2D/3D forward and inverse modelling (resistivity + IP).
- R2/cR2/R3t/cR3t/ResIPy are freeware inversion and modelling programs provided by A. Binley, Lancaster Environment Center. It is a Windows executable for 2D and 3D direct and inverse modelling of resistivity (and IP for cR2 and cR3t). A new Python code has been released: ResIPy (Blanchy *et al.*, 2020). It can be downloaded at GitHub for Windows, MacOS and Linux platforms (<https://github.com/hkexgroup/resipy>).
- 3DINV is a freeware software for the 3D inversion of tomographic resistivity data developed by the laboratory of Geophysical-Satellite Remote Sensing and Archaeo-environment (IMS-FORTH Rethymnon) (Papadopoulos *et al.*, 2011). The link is no longer working: https://www.ims.forth.gr/en/index_main.php?c=90&l=g&d=7. It can be used for academic and research purposes.

General comments:

Despite the fact that resistivity imaging is not the most frequently used method in geophysics applied to archaeology (possibly due to considerable work load), there exists much free code for the modelling of resistive anomalies. This is due to the wide use of ERT in other fields of geophysics and due to the work of Loke and Papadopoulos for example: ready-to-use executable codes from 1D to 3D exists. Otherwise, a Python environment is generally needed for more complex and scalable applications

P.S.

We have recently found a promising freeware: SimPEG.XYZ (Simulation and Parameter Estimation in Geophysics, <https://simpeg.xyz/>). It is an open source Python package for simulation (finite volume) and gradient based parameter estimation in geophysical applications (Cockett *et al.*, 2015). This software is based on a MIT Licence (this license does not force packages that use SIMPEG to be open source nor does it restrict commercial use). It provides simulation and inversion tools for all the methods we have discussed in this paper. SimPEG is a very active community with a forum, lots of documentation, examples of codes and weekly online meetings.

We must thank now Armin Schmidt for his careful reading. He has mentioned software packages that we missed to mention:

-1 The broad range of software available from the UBC Geophysical Inversion Facility, the team of Doug Oldenburg: https://gif.eos.ubc.ca/software/main_programs. These software (DCIP2D and 3D/MAG3D/GRAV3D/EM1DFM/EM1DTM) are available for academic, educational and commercial licensing. SimPEG seems to be derived from their previous expertise. A very interesting Internet site with on-line courses, toolkit, books, etc. including SimPEG is available at <http://geosci.xyz>.

-2 Seismic Unix (often called 'SU') for the processing of GPR and seismic reflection data (<https://wiki.seismic-unix.org/doku.php>). The CWP/SU is an open source seismic utilities package originally created by the Center for Wave Phenomena (CWP) at the Colorado School of Mines (CSM) and is more than 50 years old. One must have a Unix or Unix-like environment to run SU. This package offers more than 450 processing and auxiliary tools....

-3 RESINVM3D is a MATLAB package for inverting 3D DC Resistivity and Electrical Resistivity Tomography data. It is a SEG sponsored package developed in 2006 and is seems no more active (<https://github.com/xiaoyingpu/RESINVM3D-mod>).

I am sure I miss lots of packages here, but this list is open now to new contributors...

Michel Dabas, Paris the 24h of March 2020

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Geophysical Modelling Software Informations

Software Name	Geophysical Method						
	Owner	Web Site	User Mode	Source	Modelling dimension	Forward solution	Reference
Electrical Resistivity - Induced Polarization							
InvVERIS	Emtomo	https://www	Commercial	Executable	1		
pyGIMLI-BERT	Günther T, R	https://www	Free	Open source	2 and 3	Finite-differ	Günther, T.,
RES1D	Loke MH	http://www	Free	Executable	1	Linear filter	
RES2Dmod /3Dmod	Loke MH	http://www	Free	Executable	2	Finite-differ	
RES2DINV 3DINV	Loke MH	www.geotomo	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3	Finite-differ	
DC_2DPro /3DPro	KIGAM (Kore	http://www	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3	Finite-eleme	Kim, J., 2009
SensInv2D/3D	Crosswellins	http://geotc	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3	SIRT/MSIRT	
2DIP/TS2DIP	Zonge	http://www	Commercial	Executable	2	Finite-eleme	
EarthImager2D / 3D	Advanced G	http://www	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3		
R2/cR2/R3t/cR3t /ResIPy	Binley A	http://www	Free	Executable	2 and 3	Finite-differ	Binley A, 20
RESINVM3D	SEG	https://github	Free	Open source	3		
3DInv		http://www	Free	Open source			
GPR							
ReflexW	Sandmeier K	https://www	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3	Finite-Differ	
GPRSIM	Goodman D	https://www	Commercial	Executable	2	Ray tracing	Goodman D
GPRslice	Goodman D	https://www	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3		
gprMax	Giannopoulc	https://www	Free	Open source	2 and 3	Finite-Differ	Warren, C.,
VIY3	Viy	https://viy.u	Free	Executable	2 and 3		
GREDED HD 3D	IDS corp.	https://idsgg	Commercial	Executable			
MATGPR	Tzanis	http://users	Free and lice	Open source	2	Finite-Differ	Tschanis A., M
RGPR	Huber	http://eman	Free	Open source	2		Huber E. and
Magnetics and Gravimetry							
MAG2DATA	Stocco S		Free	Open source	2 and 2.5		Stocco S, Go
Potensoft	ArISOY MÖ		Free	Open source	3		ArISOY MÖ, I

Geophysical Modelling Software Informations

Software Name	Geophysical Method						
	Owner	Web Site	User Mode	Source	Modelling dimension	Forward solution	Reference
POTENT Software	Geophysical		Commercial	Executable	2 and 3D		
GM-SYS	Northwest G		Commercial	Executable	2D		
GMM	G-Trend Ltd.		?	?	2 and 2.5	?	
MOD3D	Igor Cerovsk	https://github.com	Free	Open source	3D	formulae for	
IGMAS+	Univ. Kiel	http://www.igmas.de	?	Executable	3D	Integral eq.	IGMAS+ a ne
GMG	Uieda	https://btoz.com	Free	Open source	2D	Talwani eq.	Uieda, L, Oliv
	Seismics						
ReflexW	Sandmeier K	https://www.reflexw.com	Commercial	Executable	2 and 3	Finite-Differ	
Seismic Un*x	Colorado Sci	https://wiki.seis.cmu.edu	Free	Open source	1 to 3		
	Electromagnetics						
Inv2DVLF	Monteiro Sa	http://emto.com	Licensed	Executable	2	Finite-Element	Monteiro Sa
pyGIMLI	Günther T, R	https://www.pygimli.org	Free	Open source	1 to 3	Finite-differ	Rücker C, Gü
FDEM1D	Univ. Ghent	https://github.com	Free	Open source	1	Finite-differ	ivity Modeling

General software

DCIP2D and 3D/MAG3D/GRA	UBC	https://github.com	Edu. Licence	Open source	1 to 3		
SIMPEG.XYZ	Community	https://simpeg.github.io	Free	Open source	1 to 3	Finite-Element	Cockett, Rov
PyGIMLI	Günther T, R	https://www.pygimli.org	Free	Open source	1 to 3	Finite-differ	Rücker C, Gü